

An approach to modelling envelope airtightness in multi-family social housing in Mediterranean Europe based on the situation in Spain

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Building hygrothermal performance, indoor air quality and energy consumption depend heavily on envelope airtightness. Over the last three decades, single-family dwellings have been amply studied in this respect by researchers in North Europe, the United States and Canada. However, very few studies have been conducted on airtightness in multi-family housing in warm climates such as Mediterranean Europe. This paper aims to enhance the understanding of building airtightness in early twenty-first-century multi-family buildings in southern Spain. Blower Door tests were conducted in 45 units in seven such buildings. The main airtightness parameter values found are reported and compared to the data for other buildings in southern Europe. The paper includes a statistical analysis of the findings, characterises building types and describes the protocol used to identify and quantify air leakage pathways. The conclusion drawn is that although a rough predictive model can be developed, the results are widely scattered due to the impact of the random component of manual construction, even in buildings with identical construction characteristics and types. The values recorded are nonetheless consistent with the findings for other European surveys.

Keywords

Airtightness, residential buildings, Blower Door test, air infiltration, southern Europe

Abbreviations

- V_{50} : air leakage rate at 50 Pa across the building envelope, including the flow rate through joints, fissures and surface pores (m^3/h)
- Q_{env} : air flow (m^3/h) across the building envelope
- Δp : pressure differential (Pa)
- n : air flow exponent
- C_{env} : air flow (or leakage) coefficient.
- N : number of dwellings
- Z : climate zone
- FA : façade area (m^2)
- S : gross floor area (m^2)
- V : volume (m^3)
- WA : window area (m^2)
- WP : window contour (perimeter) (m)
- WIN : winter severity
- SUM : summer severity
- n_{50} : air change rate at 50 Pa (h^{-1})
- w_{50} : specific leakage area at 50 Pa ($\text{m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^2)$)
- f_{50} : air leakage rate per unit of façade area at 50 Pa ($\text{m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^2)$)
- p_{50} : air leakage rate per unit of window perimeter at 50 Pa ($\text{m}^3/\text{h}\cdot\text{m}$)
- U -value: thermal transmission ($\text{W}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K})$)
- T : Monthly mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- TM : Monthly mean of daily maximum temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- Tm : Monthly mean of daily minimum temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- H : Monthly mean relative humidity (%)
- I : sunshine hours (h)

1. Introduction

At this time, the residential sector accounts for 17 % of Spain's final energy and 25 % of its electric power consumption. Approximately 48 % of that demand is estimated to be attributable to heating and cooling systems, values that are on the rise in Mediterranean areas [1]. As Spain is one of the largest countries, area-wise, in Mediterranean Europe, the hygrothermal performance, energy consumption and indoor air quality of its housing stock are sufficiently representative to be extrapolated to similar regions in southern Europe. In the wake of the transposition into Spanish Regulation (CTE, 2006) [2] of the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) and its provisions on thermal envelope requirements, airtightness may be regarded as one of the factors with greatest impact on hygrothermal performance, energy consumption and indoor air quality in modern homes. Airtightness values and solar radiation-induced thermal loads (in both winter and summer) are instrumental in determining the actual energy demand in Mediterranean multi-family buildings. This applies to heating as

well as cooling [3, 4, 5] and consequently to building energy strategies and performance labelling. Identification of air leakage pathways is a prerequisite to proposing construction solutions to improve building airtightness in compliance with the EU's 20-20-20 objectives [6].

Building envelope airtightness has become a standard area of research in the USA [7], where the most comprehensive databases and widest variety of infiltration models are available [8, 9, 10, 11]. In particular, the LBNL air leakage measurements database developed by Chan et al. [12] and the DOE's Multifamily Envelope Leakage Model [12] are very widely used. Drawing from an extensive review of measurements taken across the country, the former developed a revised model for single-family detached housing. The latter described a model for multi-family buildings which is, however, scantily applicable to southern Europe, where building types, construction techniques and climate vary immensely from the parameters for which the model was developed. Despite these constraints, both can be used as benchmarks for comparison.

Intense research is also underway in northern and central Europe [13,14,15], where building airtightness is extensively regulated. In southern Europe, dwelling airtightness and its relationship to the main air inlets has been studied more profusely in France than in any other country. There, multi-family units have been shown to be more airtight than single-family homes and the construction system used has been identified as one of the major factors affecting the results [16, 17]. Legislation on airtightness is lacking in other southern European countries, although insightful papers have been published on conditions in Greece [18], Italy [19] and Portugal [20, 21]. The Italian study covered 20 buildings of different types and in different seasons, while in Portugal the object of research was social housing, namely two multi-family buildings surveyed before and after retrofitting. The mean V_{50} values found by the latter for an area comparable to the region studied here were 8.9 h^{-1} prior to and 6.8 h^{-1} after refurbishment.

The most prominent infiltration studies conducted in Spain include research by Meiss and Feijo, who found a mean V_{50} of 6.26 h^{-1} [22] for the 13 homes measured and by Tiberio and Branchi, who ran the most extensive survey in the region to date, testing 150 recently built dwellings. Although the data were widely scattered, with a mean V_{50} of 3.50 h^{-1} , the distribution by low, medium and high airtightness showed that as a rule today's buildings lie in the medium category [23]. While the data reported in these papers are of interest from the standpoint of characterisation, they refer to north-central Spain, a region with a fairly cold continental climate reminiscent of central European construction techniques geared to airtightness, insulation and effective heating systems. Building conditions there consequently vary widely with respect to the warmer areas of the country. In contrast, a study by Montoya et al. addressing the less directly related issue of protection against air pollution due to toxic gas release, adopted an approach relevant to the present research [24]. Although that study involved no field tests and focused on single-family homes, it proposed a regional prediction model that differed from the Chan model and drew from a database of French tests (CETE Lyon). The authors also proposed a methodology for extrapolating the data based on housing type similarities.

Therefore, the studies conducted in southern Europe have yet to deliver a large body of data

enough to identify the actual impact of airtightness on the energy efficiency of the residential buildings of the area, and the link with regional construction systems.

This article analyses a comprehensive suite of field data with the aim of enhancing the understanding of housing stock energy performance in an area highly representative of Mediterranean Europe. It focuses on multi-family units built in southern Spain in the first decade of the twenty-first century. The field campaign findings are set out, air leakage pathways are characterised, the scatter observed in envelope performance is discussed and a predictive model is proposed.

2. Context

Single-family dwellings account for 64 % of the total European housing stock, although in the southern part of the continent, particularly in Italy and Spain, multi-family buildings prevail [25]. These countries also have a large stock of social housing, most of which adopts multi-family configurations [26] built to minimum construction quality standards [27]. While social housing can be defined in a number of ways, here it is meant in the broadest sense: housing that receives some manner of government subsidy or assistance [28].

Substantial improvements will be needed in these buildings in the years to come, both to improve indoor habitability and to comply with the energy efficiency standards for nearly zero energy buildings laid down in the EPBD [29] and in the EU's 20-20-20 objectives [30]. This is going to call for a huge effort in Spain and in other Mediterranean countries to improve the existing housing stock by means of effective, optimised energy intervention and refurbishment techniques. One of the main aims of refurbishment policy should be to optimise available public and private resources. Scantly effective retrofitting should be avoided to attain genuine energy savings while reaching the primary aim, the enhancement of indoor comfort.

These considerations are applicable to a significant portion of Europe: its entire Mediterranean flank, from southern Portugal to Turkey.

The area has a temperate climate, with mild temperatures that fluctuate only narrowly throughout the year. The winters are not very cold (with temperatures dipping below freezing only exceptionally), and although warm, the summers are not torrid. While the climate varies with the lay of the land, it is clearly distinct from conditions in central and northern Europe. The area is classified as Köppen Csa and Csb [31].

Albeit with regional variations, multi-family building architecture and construction are similar across the area [32] and differ widely from the solutions in place in central and northern European countries, especially where social housing is concerned [33]. Many of these solutions are a legacy inherited from the nineteen sixties and seventies residential construction boom [34]. The area's inhabitants share more than a similar climate, however, for social and cultural mores around housing use and occupancy are likewise analogous.

The reinforced concrete frame and continuous concrete slab construction that characterises medium-rise multi-dwelling housing, especially social housing, in Mediterranean cities, results in very airtight inter-storey compartmentation. The outer enclosures typically consist of brick or block (heavy- or medium-weight walls), usually with an inner cavity and several layers of plaster on the inside. Lightweight façades are uncommon.

As a rule this social buildings has been concibed as Natural Ventilated based on the understanding of the climate as benign, and generally lacks built-in heating or air conditioning systems. Users meet their heating needs with portable electrical radiators that in most cases are energetically inefficient and unable to provide for an even distribution of comfortable temperatures [35]. Nor is this housing fitted with ducted, whole-home cooling systems. , despite the warm summers that characterise the area. As a result, homeowners tend to install room-size split AC-units a posteriori.

These buildings were not generally fitted with mechanically controlled ventilation systems until the entry into effect of the Technical Building Code in 2007 [2]. Prior to that date, bathroom and kitchen ventilation was based on the stack effect across static vents. Such extraction systems are often ineffective. Where indoor air quality in Mediterranean housing is not particularly poor it is thanks to the uncontrolled inflow of air through the building envelope (infiltration) or voluntary ventilation (manual operation of windows).

Envelope thermal-performance is average in such buildings, with medium-to-low thermal mass and wall thermal transmittance values on the order of 0.5-1.5 W/m²K. Artificial heating and cooling are needed to ensure comfortable indoor temperatures in the winter and summer under normal outdoor conditions. The absence of built-in HVAC is one of the major reasons for the indoor temperature dispersion typically found in this housing [35,36].

3. Methods

Field research to assess building airtightness was conducted between late 2011 and early 2013 in a number of locations in southern Spain (Andalusia) to ensure coverage of the various intra-regional climates. Pressurisation and depressurisation were measured with a Blower Door Test System, later supplemented with infrared thermography and smoke tests to identify specific infiltration pathways.

3.1. Sampling

The study was conducted on 45 homes in seven open gallery-type buildings in southern Spain. This building type, characterised by outdoor walkways on all floors from which each individual unit is accessed (Figure 1), was chosen for a number of reasons.

- It is very commonly found in Mediterranean residential buildings, especially in social housing.

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CS1	Seville	B	4	2004	Hinged	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS2	Seville	B	4	2006	Sliding	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS3	Cordoba	B	4	2007	Hinged	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS4	Malaga	A	3	2007	Sliding	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS5	Almeria	A	4	2008	Sliding	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS6	Granada	C	3	2003	Hinged	Roller blinds	5/7	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen
CS7	Jaen	C	4	2011	Sliding	Roller blinds	6	Passive vents in bathroom and kitchen

Table 1: Location, climate zone, year of construction and characterisation of the buildings studied.

The units chosen in the seven buildings had similar floor areas (Table 2) and construction solutions to enhance comparability and ensure that generally applicable conclusions on performance could be drawn.

The sample consisted in reinforced concrete frame, continuous slab buildings with ceramic or cement tile flooring. Only kitchens and bathrooms had continuous suspended ceilings. Vertical envelope consisted in cavity-insulated walls: ceramic-brick wall outside, air chamber with insulation panel, and thin ceramic-brick plastered inner sheeting. Party walls consisted in thin hollowbrick (approximately 15 cm thick) partitions, plastered on both sides. All windows, whether side-hinged or horizontal-sliding, had aluminium frames and double glazing (Table 1) and were fitted with built-in roller blinds ('monoblock' system). The cross-section of a typical building solution is shown in Appendix A. The U-values for walls and windows were similar for all the buildings. As these units had no built-in air conditioning or heating, there was no horizontal or vertical ductwork outside the conditioned space. This design minimises inter-storey connections, which are confined to drainage and vents in wet rooms, normally embedded in the partitions.

With construction systems based on large continuous inter-storey slabs and a paucity of internal service shafts, horizontal air leakage was minimal in these buildings, an advantage reinforced by the outdoor location of staircases and elevators. In open gallery configurations, in turn, dwellings are primarily in contact with the outdoor environment, with scant communication with other building elements as vertical shafts or stairs. The resulting lack of vertical air pathways [38] practically eliminated the stack effect. As all the units studied were one-storey dwellings, the façade would constitute the primary route for potential infiltration, along with

theventilation shafts, which could be readily sealed and insulated during the tests.

In pursuit of representative sampling, a random, stratified and proportional design was adopted. In all the buildings, at least one of the units tested was located on the lowest storey, one on an intermediate storey and a third under the roof to study the possible impact of horizontal enclosures and the stack effect resulting from differences in height within a given building [39].

Table 2 lists the characteristics of the units in the seven buildings, where *Z* represents the winter climate, *N* the number of storeys, *S* and *V* the mean floor area and volume, respectively, *FA* the mean façade area, *WA* the mean window area and *WP* the mean window perimeter. The standard deviation (σ) for all the aforementioned variables is also shown.

Building	Z	N	S		V		FA		WA		WP	
			Mean (m ²)	σ	Mean (m ³)	σ	Mean (m ²)	σ	Mean (m ²)	σ	Mean (m)	σ
CS1	B	7	64.51	6.01	176	16.46	54.29	2.92	8.99	1.87	30.84	3.82
CS2	B	5	70.40	0.00	183	0.00	47.20	0.00	8.20	0.00	28.00	0.00
CS3	B	8	70.00	0.00	185	0.00	46.40	0.00	9.10	0.00	30.30	0.00
CS4	A	4	68.63	21.9	188	60.08	60.60	19.77	12.08	3.33	40.38	10.24
CS5	A	8	68.89	1.72	188	5.79	46.91	0.82	9.00	0.67	29.78	1.44
CS6	C	8	69.88	0.23	175	0.51	45.45	0.63	16.03	0.86	42.78	2.44
CS7	C	5	69.56	0.49	174	1.24	34.06	1.05	8.90	0.00	26.40	0.00
Mean		45	68.80	6.50	181	17.90	47.52	8.50	10.43	3.00	32.71	6.70

Table 2: Characteristics of the buildings selected

Although the units in the buildings selected had similar gross floor areas, their mean window areas and perimeters and floor areas differed substantially, favouring statistical analysis. Under these arrangements, the possible effect of each of these three parameters on airtightness could be determined.

3.2. Pressurised fan airtightness measurements

The field study consisted in pressurisation/depressurisation tests performed with a Blower Door device supplemented with infrared thermography and smoke tests, a technique generally accepted as valid by the scientific community [40]. The test was conducted with a Minneapolis Blower Door™ system running Tectite software. Spaces around all manner of openings were sealed with a suitable material. Building envelopes were assessed to Spanish and European standard UNE-EN 13829: 2002, Method B [41]. All the vents, mechanical and otherwise, in bathrooms and kitchens, including smoke extractors in the latter, were sealed and all other outdoor openings (windows) closed.

In addition to the Method B trials, a number of other pressurisation/depressurisation tests were conducted, in which the sealing set-up was varied (Figure 9). Alternative tests P5 (bathrooms and kitchens sealed off) and P6 (only bathrooms sealed off) proved to be of particular interest to locate air pathways. The findings were used to compare the performance of the envelope

enclosing dry rooms as opposed to the wet rooms that are more prone to uncontrolled cracks and openings around service ductways.

Each unit was regarded to constitute a single volume, inasmuch as energy performance was practically even throughout. The test consisted in positioning the fan on the outside door to remove (depressurise) or force (pressurise) air from or into the dwelling to a positive or negative pressure of 50 Pa, and subsequently measuring the airflow at 5 Pa intervals. All windows in the unit were closed and all the interior doors left open during the test. To prevent outdoor conditions from affecting the results, tests were only run when the wind speed was between 0 and 2 m/s [42] and the difference between the indoor and outdoor temperature was no greater than 5 °C.

The air flow rate across the building envelope (Q_{env}) was calculated from the difference in the indoor and outdoor pressure (Δp) using the following power law equation:

$$Q_{env} = C_{env} \cdot (\Delta p)^n \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where C_{env} , the air flow coefficient, depends on the size of building openings and n , the air flow exponent, characterises the flow regime, with values ranging from 0.5 for turbulent flow to 1 for laminar flow [43]. The study of air flow exponent n identifies the type of air pathway, which helps characterise the usual infiltration pathways.

3.3. Parameters studied

3.3.1. Airtightness parameters defined in European standard UNE-EN 13829

European standard UNE-EN 13829 defines airtightness in terms of the parameters listed in Table 3.

Parameter	Name	Unit	Definition
V_{50}	Air Leakage rate at 50 Pa	m^3/h	Air flow across the building envelope, including the flow rate through joints, fissures and surface pores
n_{50}	Air change rate at 50 Pa	h^{-1}	Infiltration air flow rate per internal volume (V)
w_{50}	Specific leakage area at 50 Pa	$m^3/(h \cdot m^2)$	Relationship between the rate of infiltrated air and the floor area (S)

Table 3: Airtightness parameters defined in European standard UNE-EN 13829

The V_{50} values (air leakage rate at 50 Pa) were weighted to ensure the comparability of the results for the units studied, giving rise to the other two parameters in the table: n_{50} was found by weighting V_{50} by unit volume and w_{50} by weighting air leakage at 50 Pa by unit area. Inasmuch as it delivered a standardised value, n_{50} was chosen as the key indicator.

3.3.2. Airtightness parameters not included in UNE-EN 13829

A number of parameters not included in European standard EN 13829 were also studied to identify the main sources of infiltration in façades and façade openings. These parameters, listed in Table 4, were associated with envelope design [43].

Parameter	Name	Unit	Definition
f_{50}	Air leakage rate per unit of façade area at 50 Pa	$m^3/(h \cdot m^2)$	Ratio between V_{50} and the façade area (FA)
p_{50}	Air leakage rate per unit of window perimeter at 50 Pa	$m^3/(h \cdot m)$	Ratio between V_{50} and the size of the openings (WP)

Table 4: Airtightness parameters not included in UNE-EN 13829

4. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The V_{50} values obtained in the Blower Door test and the statistical parameters for each building are given in Table 5. Standard deviation varied from 1 to 31 % of the value, depending on the building. The divide between the high and low values was even wider, with the highest nearly doubling the lowest in buildings CS1 and CS4.

<i>Building</i>	Number of units	<i>Mean</i> (m^3/h)	<i>Median</i> (m^3/h)	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Highest</i> (m^3/h)	<i>Lowest</i> (m^3/h)
CS1	7	842	719	218	664	1210
CS2	5	1536	1531	24	1508	1565
CS3	8	1311	1281	136	1187	1605
CS4	4	819	824	232	547	1082
CS5	8	732	739	80	566	843
CS6	8	827	823	97	646	978
CS7	5	1336	1281	88	1261	1438
Mean	45	1033	920	322	547	1605

Table 5: V_{50} values (m^3/h)

The results of the airtightness tests in the 45 case studies shown in Figure 2, were weighted by volume to be able to compare the samples on as even a playing field as possible. Considerable scatter was found, both among and within buildings. The relative stability of the statistical parameters observed for CS2 and CS7 denoted uniform construction quality.

Figure 2: n_{50} values for 45 housing units in seven buildings

The highest n_{50} value was $8.7 h^{-1}$, found for building CS3, whereas the lowest, $3.2 h^{-1}$, was recorded in building CS5. The mean of $5.72 h^{-1}$ deviated considerably from the recommended values in place in other countries for classifying a building as airtight (UNE-EN 15242:2007, [44]). While the kurtosis values (Appendix B) might be associated with a normal distribution, the coefficients of variation and the differences in standard deviation indicated that, from the standpoint of performance, the sample did not represent a single population. Four of the seven buildings exhibited leptokurtic behaviour with significant grouping around the central values, and three a platykurtic distribution with scant concentration around the central values.

The scatter observed in the values for n_{50} was attributable to the stochastic component inherent in the construction of the buildings studied. That notwithstanding, a probability distribution derived from an analysis of sample behaviour served as a basis for a model able to explain sample variation and as a reference for comparing future samples (Figure 3a). The cluster around low n_{50} values in the peak on the density curve (Figure 3b and Equation 2) denoted bias in the distribution, reinforcing the non-normality hypothesis. The data could not be fit to a normal distribution (at 95 % confidence), although they did fit a type I (maximum) extreme value distribution with a mode of 4.74 and a scale of 1.33.

Figure 3: Cumulative probability (a) and density (b), n_{50}

$$PDF: f(x) = \frac{1}{1,32955} \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{x-4,74195}{1,32955} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{x-4,74195}{1,32955} \right) \right\} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

A predictive model could be generated, subject to a tolerance limit: the n_{50} values for 86.77 % of the sample could be expected to lie between 3.2 h⁻¹ and 8.7 h⁻¹ at 95.0 % confidence. Given the bias toward lower values, 50 % of the population had n_{50} values of less than 5.23 h⁻¹.

Statistical analyses were conducted to determine the existence or otherwise of a relationship or correlation between airtightness and the values of the parameters studied: n_{50} , f_{50} and p_{50} . The tests were designed to confirm (null hypothesis) or rule out (alternative hypothesis) the existence of a single population in which performance could be explained by the volume-associated geometries of the 45 dwellings constituting the sample, the design of their envelopes or their climate zone.

In this study the null hypothesis was initially adopted, for the sample comprised a series of units with the same conceptual design, similar areas and the same construction systems. In other words, the data were initially assumed to have been drawn from different samples of the same population. Further to that assumption, the analysis of their airtightness should have yielded consistent results and comparable behaviour for these three parameters.

The statistical tests initially adopted to confirm or rule out the null hypothesis were ANOVA to check the mean; Levene to check variance; Kruskal-Wallis to check the median.

4.1. Exponent n

The value of exponent n ranged from 0.54 to 0.64 with a median of 0.58±0.026 (STD). Although standardised sample bias and kurtosis lay within the range of normal distributions, that hypothesis was ruled out on the grounds of the Shapiro-Wilk test findings (95 % confidence interval). The best fit, assuming free distribution, was found for a reverse Gaussian distribution with an 87.62 % log-likelihood and 95 % confidence that 88.39 % of the distribution would lie within a range of 0.54-0.64 (Figure 4).

Figure 4: n exponent Histogram for B Method

While the generally accepted minimum for the pressure exponent is 0.65 [45], a value of 0.66 is the reference adopted in countries where airtightness standards are traditionally high, such as Canada, the Netherlands or the UK [46]. This figure is based on the fact that air leakage pathways in residential units are dominated by developing flows in cracks such that $n = 0.67$ [39]. Construction techniques and materials, not to mention the climates, found in the AIVC database (which covers Canada, Netherlands, New Zealand and USA) differ significantly from the conditions prevailing in Spain and other southern European countries, however. The values measured in countries such as Italy are usually lower, at 0.55 to 0.69 with a mean on the order of 0.60, because flow exponent n tends to be higher in leakage openings with larger flow resistance [19] than those found in the Mediterranean area.

Values of around 0.6 are associated with leakage through the interfaces between openings and their opaque surrounds.

4.2. Dependence on geometric characteristics

A series of statistical tests was conducted on the premise that envelope morphology may justify airtightness performance. Building geometric characteristics are plotted against V_{50} in Figure 5. While the relationship between V_{50} and parameter V appeared to follow an upward pattern and all the other relationships the contrary, the values were too scattered to draw valid conclusions.

Figure 5: V_{50} vs parameters V , FA , WA and WP

The statistical findings for parameters n_{50} (volume), p_{50} (opening size) and f_{50} (façade area) are given in Appendix B. As noted in the methodological section, these findings were verified by ANOVA and the Levene and Kruskal-Wallis tests, the results of which are listed in Table 6.

	ANOVA		Levene		Kruskal-Wallis	
	F	P	Value	P	Value	P
n_{50}	49.78	0.00	2.54	0.036	36.03	0.00
f_{50}	100.48	0.00	3.03	0.016	36.89	0.00
p_{50}	100.13	0.00	3.00	0.017	38.55	0.00

Table 6: ANOVA, Levene and Kruskal-Wallis test results

In the ANOVA for n_{50} , the key indicator, variance was divided into an inter- and a within-group component. The F-statistic, here equal to 49.78, is the ratio between the estimated inter- and estimated within-group variance. The p-value calculated for the F-statistic was under 0.05, denoting a statistically significant difference among the seven mean values at 95 % confidence. Similar conclusions were drawn when ANOVAs were conducted for f_{50} and p_{50} .

The Levene and Kruskal-Wallis tests were run to supplement analysis of variance. In the former, the p-value was of particular interest: at 0.036 and hence less than 0.05, it indicated a statistically significant difference among the standard deviations at 95 % confidence. In the latter, the p-value, likewise under 0.05, denoted a statistically significant difference among the seven median values at 95 % confidence.

Ruling out the possibility of aberrant values for n_{50} , f_{50} and p_{50} , the null hypothesis had to be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The inference was that the seven buildings in the sample did not constitute a single population from which the three parameters could be estimated.

The cumulative frequency curves and boxplots in Figure 6 show the results of the least significant difference (LSD) test, from which the three sub-groups or trends identified for n_{50} , the five for f_{50} and the four for p_{50} were derived. Intra-sample dependence and sampling errors were ruled out.

Figure 6: Cumulative frequency curves and box and whisker plots for the groups identified in the seven buildings studied

4.3. Dependence on climate zone

The dataset did not appear to corroborate the intuitive assumption that as a rule, building construction seeks greater airtightness in colder than in warmer areas [44].

Hence, the initial hypothesis was that the volume-weighted infiltration values (n_{50}) were not dependent upon the climate zone where buildings were located.

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The explanation may be that all the buildings in the sample were located in southern Spain and despite climate differences from one area to another, shared construction solutions, architecture and usage. Initially, then, location was assumed to have no impact on the prediction of parameter n_{50} (null hypothesis).

Table 7 lists the statistics for n_{50} by climate zone and Figure 7 reproduces the cumulative frequency curves, likewise by climate zone.

Z	Number of units	Mean (h^{-1})	Median (h^{-1})	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Lowest	Highest
A	12	4.08	4.1	0.51	12.65%	3.20	5.30
B	20	6.59	6.7	1.64	24.93%	3.90	8.70
C	13	5.86	5.3	1.59	27.14%	3.70	8.30
Mean	45	5.71	5.30	1.73	30.36%	3.20	8.70

Table 7: Statistics for n_{50} (h^{-1}) by climate zone

Figure 7: Cumulative frequency curves for n_{50} (h^{-1}) by climate zone

Lastly, a chi-square test was run (with a test value of 65.97) to determine whether the assumption of independence between n_{50} and climate zone could be rejected. Since the p-value was greater than 0.01 (0.22), independence between the two variables could not be ruled out at 99 % confidence. In light of those results and the distribution of the values, then, n_{50} was not necessarily dependent upon climate zone.

4.4. Multiple linear correlation approach to developing a predictive model

While acknowledging the stochastic nature of these values due to their association with construction processes, a predictive model could be proposed, subject to a band of uncertainty.

This model may prove useful when forecasting expected behaviour and establishing a framework for comparison.

Pearson's bivariate correlation coefficients were found for the geometric parameters associated with the n_{50} values to ascertain the existence or otherwise of inter-variable dependence. The correlation coefficients ranged from -0.98 to 0.75. For V , they denoted a statistically significant p-value of 0.003, which was somewhat higher for WA and even higher for WP .

In light of this possible dependence, which even if present would not prove causality, a series of ANOVAs and linear regression analyses were conducted to determine whether infiltration in the group of dwellings studied could be predicted with a model based on their geometric characteristics, as the initial hypothesis would appear to indicate.

A factorial analysis was run on the independent variables in the linear regression model. This procedure, which excludes the least significant variables in the model, reduced the number to the four with the highest statistical significance (Figure 8). All six variables, S , V , FA , WA , WP and Z , were included in the factorial analysis to obtain a better fit. As expected, FA and Z (climatic zone) exhibited low statistical significance and were disregarded.

Figure 8: Component+residual plot for n_{50} and different parameters

The predictive model proposed can be expressed as shown below (Equation 3), with the

coefficients listed in Table 8.

$$n_{50} = \alpha \times S - \beta \times V - \gamma \times WA + \delta \times WP \quad \text{Eq.(3)}$$

Parameter	Coefficient	Estimate	Standard error
S	α	1.019	0.101
V	β	-0.353	0.044
WA	γ	-1.763	0.360
WP	δ	0.549	0.161

Table 8: Predictive linear regression model: coefficients

The model proposed afforded a good approximation, explaining 98.12 % of the variation in the dependent variable (n_{50}). Although the estimated error was significant (0.849 h^{-1}), it provided a more accurate fit than the standard deviation of the measurements (approximately halving the width of the fluctuation band). Barring any prior knowledge of geometric factors, the best prediction was that the air flow in a dwelling would be around $5.72 \pm 1.74 \text{ h}^{-1}$ (Table 5).

This model is proposed to predict envelope air-tightness in the social housing stock built in southern Spain, based on a sample of 45 gallery-type buildings. The model was developed using multiple linear regression.

4.5. Typical air leakage pathways

The primary air leakage pathways [47] were identified with infrared thermography or smoke during the Blower Door test. These tests were run during the winter with the heating on and the rooms depressurised (ISO 18434-1: 2008) [48].

In the building type studied, the envelopes in all the units were bounded in part by the outdoors and in part by other units. Buildings were tested in detail, sealing off the parts of the unit where air could flow in from the party walls, to determine the percentage of infiltration attributable to the outdoor enclosure (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Sealing protocols to locate air leakage pathways. The findings for the various types of test (protocols 1 to 9) were analysed to determine the relative weight of each dwelling component in overall air infiltration. The trend identified in this suite of tests reproduced the behaviour observed in the detailed analysis conducted on building CS2, albeit with a significant rate of variation (Figure 10).

Infiltration between adjacent units was found to be scantily significant: just 3.6 % of the total.

Figure 10: Dwelling airtightness, contribution by component

These tests also showed that air leakage took place primarily across the vertical envelope, particularly in dry rooms where most of the windows are located. Nonetheless, plumbing, electrical and ventilation ductways also contributed to infiltration. In contrast, no significant infiltration was found across horizontal elements or party walls, nor were differences observed between under-roof units and other dwellings.

As would be expected in façades of the type found on these buildings, the main air pathways were at the interface between windows and opaque enclosures. The wide variability recorded in the test values may have been the result of the manual construction procedures deployed in this type of buildings, inducing differences in dwellings in one and the same building. Hens identified the cause of such variations to be poor workmanship [49]. In this study, the findings for different window types were compared to corroborate that conclusion. No relationship was found between window closure type (hinged or sliding) and infiltration rates, whereas behaviour was observed to vary widely within each type of window.

The whisker box in Figure 11 shows the proportion of leakage attributable to the wet (kitchen and bathroom) and dry rooms. Note that over half of the total leakage was associated with the envelope around dry rooms (in the Method A test, i.e., with the dwelling in use). Nonetheless, these values were subject to 17 % variability. The proportion attributable to wet rooms was lower, and higher in bathrooms (from under 10 % to 20 %) than in kitchens (under 7 %). Method B, i.e., considering measurements for the envelope alone (disregarding vents and permanent openings), yielded the following values: 72.69 % for the dry room envelope, 18.85 % for the bathroom envelope and 8.71 % for the kitchen envelope.

Figure 11: Proportion of infiltration accounted for by room type

4.6. Comparison to other regions

The present findings were compared to the results reported for similar studies on multi-family dwellings conducted in southern Europe. Research focusing on single-family homes or with a small number of cases was disregarded. When the information was provided on the date of construction, the data were broken down for separate analysis of the dwellings built within more or less the same time frame as the ones studied here, in particular units built to legislation deriving from the EPBD. The n_{50} values are reproduced in Figure 12, which also shows the intervals that define the low, medium and high airtightness categories set out in European and international standard EN-ISO 137900 [50] and the number of tests run to establish the representativeness of the values.

Figure 12: Values for European multi-family dwellings

The figure shows information on the following datasets: Italy^a, overall total [19]; Italy^b, dwellings built in 2001-2010 [19]; Portugal^a [20]; Portugal^b, refurbished dwellings [21]; Portugal^c, non-refurbished dwellings [21]; N-Spain^a, dwellings built in 1979-2007 [22]; N-Spain^b, EPBD dwellings [22]; N-Spain^c, mainly EPBD dwellings [23]; S-Spain, present study.

The above analysis revealed that the S-Spain n_{50} values, which lay predominantly in the medium band, were in line with the findings for similar units in the Mediterranean area. These values were lower than in other newer buildings in northern and central Spain, built after the transposition of the EPBD, and lower as well than Italian buildings erected more recently. The lowest n_{50} values (high airtightness) were found for the oldest buildings (Italy^a and N-Spain^a), while the highest (low airtightness) were recorded in the Portuguese dwellings (Portugal^{a,b,c}) even after refurbishment. The scatter observed in the n_{50} values, while significant, was similar to the findings reported for other Mediterranean regions.

The n_{50} values recorded here were higher than required in northern and central European countries' design standards, where housing airtightness has long been the object of regulation. The reference n_{50} value in Germany and Norway is 3 h^{-1} and in Finland, 4 h^{-1} . While some of the dwellings in this study exhibited values nearly as low as those benchmarks, others, in keeping with results reported by the earlier studies analysed here, doubled the score.

5. Conclusions

The air permeability readings at 50 Pa for 45 multi-family units with open galleries built in southern Spain after 2000 averaged 5.72 h^{-1} . This value was higher than energy efficiency standards and recommendations for European buildings, although similar to the results

reported for northern Spain and other southern European countries such as Italy and Portugal.

The study revealed a wide scatter in the airtightness values recorded and highlighted the difficulties involved in proposing an accurate predictive model. That the scatter for parameter n_{50} was greater than the mean values is an indication of flaws in building envelope continuity. The values for the entire sample ranged from 3.2 to 8.7 h⁻¹ and in some cases the high value in a given building doubled the low value in the same building. The value of exponent n ranged from 0.56 to 0.61 in all the measurements performed. Values on the order of 0.6 are associated with leakage at interfaces between openings and their opaque surrounds.

Despite the uncertainty generated by the artisanal façade construction methods typical of this housing stock in southern Europe, the model developed was able to predict the degree of airtightness in these dwellings with acceptable accuracy. That model may be particularly useful to compare airtightness values for buildings erected in the same time frame. It should be regarded as a regional tool, tailored to southern European construction and architecture that aims to be an alternative to the more universal models developed to date. In addition, the probabilistic model for behaviour proposed here is applicable to the assessment and construction of models for analysing the housing stock.

In light of the difficulties described to build a reliable predictive model, no design solutions for buildings and their envelopes that would enhance airtightness can be put forward. Consequently, efforts should focus on construction per se, seeking more assembly-sensitive solutions and reinforcing the control of workmanship in openings and interfaces with the opaque plane. Tests that measure infiltration rates must also be conducted. No infiltration was observed at the interface between the deck slab and vertical members in the dwellings tested, with no perceptible differences between under-roof and intermediate units, nor was any detected at party walls. Therefore, improvements should focus on the joints around façade openings.

This study revealed the need to individualise airtightness surveys to be able to identify the main air infiltration pathways across the envelope and hence apply protocols both for construction quality and ascertainment of the condition of buildings with a view to energy refurbishment. Pressurisation techniques have proven to be a cost-effective approach to assessing and improving the energy performance of buildings in general and residential buildings in southern Europe in particular.

Given the impact of infiltration on energy demand and consumption in residential buildings, airtightness should be regarded as an instrumental factor for the energy assessment of the existing housing stock and its refurbishment to meet nearly zero energy building (NZEB) aspirations in the southern Mediterranean.

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Appendix A

Figure A.1: Plan view of CS1.

Figure A.2: Plan view of CS2.

Figure A.3: Plan view of CS3.

Figure A.4: Plan view of CS4.

Figure A.5: Plan view of CS5.

Figure A.6: Plan view of CS6.

Figure A.7: Plan view of CS7.

Figure A.8: Cross-section of construction system

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Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	10.9	16.0	5.7	71	183
February	12.5	18.1	7.0	67	189
March	15.6	21.9	9.2	59	220
April	17.3	23.4	11.1	57	238
May	20.7	27.2	14.2	53	293
June	25.1	32.2	18.0	48	317
July	28.2	36.0	20.3	44	354
August	27.9	35.5	20.4	48	328
September	25.0	31.7	18.2	54	244
October	20.2	26.0	14.4	62	216
November	15.1	20.2	10.0	70	181
December	11.9	16.6	7.3	74	154

Table A.1: Seville climatic data (Z = B4)

Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	9.3	14.9	3.6	76	174
February	11.1	17.4	4.9	71	186
March	14.4	21.3	7.4	64	218
April	16.0	22.8	9.3	60	235
May	20.0	27.4	12.6	55	288
June	24.7	32.8	16.5	48	323
July	28.0	36.9	19.0	41	363
August	28.0	36.5	19.4	43	336
September	24.2	31.6	16.9	52	248
October	19.1	25.1	13.0	66	204
November	13.5	19.1	7.8	73	180
December	10.4	15.3	5.5	79	148

Table A.2: Cordoba climatic data (Z = B4)

Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	12.1	16.8	7.4	69	180
February	12.9	17.7	8.2	68	180
March	14.7	19.6	9.8	67	222
April	16.3	21.4	11.1	63	244
May	19.3	24.3	14.2	59	292
June	23.0	28.1	18.0	58	329
July	25.5	30.5	20.5	58	347
August	26.0	30.8	21.1	61	316
September	23.5	28.2	18.8	65	255

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October	19.5	24.1	15.0	70	215
November	15.7	20.1	11.3	71	172
December	13.2	17.5	8.9	72	160

Table A.3: Malaga climatic data (Z = A3)

Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	12.6	16.9	8.3	67	194
February	13.3	17.6	9.0	67	191
March	15.1	19.6	10.6	65	232
April	17.0	21.4	12.5	62	261
May	19.7	24.1	15.3	63	297
June	23.5	27.9	18.9	61	325
July	26.1	30.5	21.7	60	342
August	26.7	31.0	22.4	63	315
September	24.2	28.4	20.0	65	256
October	20.4	24.5	16.3	68	218
November	16.4	20.5	12.3	67	183
December	13.8	17.9	9.6	67	178

Table A.4: Almeria climatic data (Z = A4)

Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	6.5	13.0	0.0	72	168
February	8.5	15.4	1.6	67	175
March	11.4	19.0	3.8	59	223
April	13.3	20.6	6.0	57	234
May	17.2	25.0	9.4	51	288
June	22.3	31.0	13.6	44	338
July	25.3	34.8	15.7	38	372
August	24.8	34.2	15.5	42	340
September	21.1	29.4	12.8	52	258
October	16.0	23.2	8.7	64	210
November	10.6	17.0	4.2	72	163
December	7.6	13.4	1.7	76	146

Table A.5: Granada climatic data (Z = C3)

Month	T (°C)	TM (°C)	Tm (°C)	H (%)	I (h)
January	8.6	12.1	5.1	70	174
February	10.3	14.0	6.6	65	186
March	13.1	17.4	8.9	59	218
April	14.5	19.0	10.0	58	235
May	18.2	23.2	13.3	55	288

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June	23.7	29.4	18.1	45	323
July	27.6	33.7	21.4	40	363
August	26.9	32.9	21.0	45	336
September	22.8	27.7	17.8	54	248
October	17.9	21.9	13.8	64	204
November	12.3	15.7	8.9	70	180
December	9.5	12.8	6.3	72	148

Table A.6: Jaen climatic data ($Z = C4$)

Appendix B

Building	Number of dwellings	Mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Lowest	Highest	Range	Standardised kurtosis
CS1	7	4.75	0.95	20.01%	3.90	6.30	2.40	-0.58
CS2	5	8.40	0.16	1.88%	8.20	8.60	0.40	-0.55
CS3	8	7.07	0.76	10.76%	6.40	8.70	2.30	1.58
CS4	4	4.45	0.64	14.27%	3.80	5.30	1.50	0.38
CS5	8	3.90	0.36	9.30%	3.20	4.40	1.20	0.71
CS6	8	4.73	0.56	11.91%	3.70	5.60	1.90	0.73
CS7	5	7.70	0.50	6.56%	7.30	8.30	1.00	-1.45
Mean	45	5.72	1.74	30.36%	3.20	8.70	5.50	-1.84

Table B.1: Statistics for n_{50} (h^{-1})

Building	Number of units	Mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Lowest	Highest	Range	Standardised kurtosis
CS1	7	15.41	3.48	22.59%	12.20	20.20	8.00	-0.88
CS2	5	32.56	0.52	1.59%	32.00	33.20	1.20	-1.10
CS3	8	28.28	2.93	10.37%	25.60	34.60	9.00	1.75
CS4	4	13.73	1.75	12.78%	11.60	15.80	4.20	0.10
CS5	8	15.55	1.77	11.40%	11.90	18.10	6.20	1.65
CS6	8	18.23	2.30	12.59%	14.30	22.20	7.90	0.78
CS7	5	39.20	1.55	3.95%	37.40	41.00	3.60	-1.09
Mean	45	22.62	9.01	39.82%	11.60	41.00	29.40	-1.30

Table B.2: Statistics for f_{50} (m^3/hm^2)

Building	Number of units	Mean	Variance	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Lowest	Highest	Range	Standardised kurtosis
CS1	7	27.20	29.87	5.47	20.09%	23.20	37.70	14.50	0.80
CS2	5	54.86	0.69	0.83	1.51%	53.90	55.90	2.00	-0.90
CS3	8	43.33	20.23	4.50	10.38%	39.20	53.00	13.80	1.70
CS4	4	20.23	5.93	2.43	12.04%	16.90	22.70	5.80	0.69
CS5	8	24.46	7.64	2.76	11.30%	19.80	28.50	8.70	0.04
CS6	8	19.48	11.33	3.37	17.28%	14.60	26.60	12.00	2.02
CS7	5	50.62	11.08	3.33	6.57%	47.80	54.50	6.70	-1.47
Mean	45	33.26	187.38	13.69	41.15%	14.60	55.90	41.30	-1.91

Table B.3: Statistics for p_{50} (m³/hm)

Predictive model	R ² : 0.981	Adjusted R ² : 0.981	Estimated standard error 0.84
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Table 11: Predictive linear regression model: summary

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